

Flavonoids from the Leaves of *Casuarina equisetifolia* Linn. (Casuarinaceae)

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Casuarina equisetifolia Linn. (Casuarinaceae) is extensively cultivated for fuel, the bark is astringent and is useful in diarrhoea and dysentery. A decoction of leaves is useful in colic, and powdered seeds are applied as plaster in headaches. The report of the presence of biflavones in *Casuarina stricta*¹, an angiosperm, led us to examine the flavonoid contents of *C. equisetifolia*.

The methanol extract of the dried and petroleum ether exhausted leaves on purification by solvent fractionation followed by adsorption chromatography on magnesium trisilicate (Woelm) yielded a number of flavonoid components. Two of the major components crystallized from methanol in aggregates of rectangular plates, m.p. 176–178° and 217–219° and one of the minor components separated from ethanol in microscopic needles, m.p. 276–278°. The homogeneity of the products was established by paper chromatographic examination in two different solvent systems, and also by TLC. The acidic cyanidin² and Wilson boric acid³ tests were positive, confirming the presence of flavonols and their glycosides.

The free aglycone, m.p. 276–278°, was identified as kaempferol by its melting and mixed melting points with an authentic sample and by the preparation of its acetate, m.p. 180–182°.⁴ The micro degradation followed by the chromatographic examination of the fragments revealed two spots, spraying with diazotized *p*-nitroaniline and bis-diazotized benzidine indistinguishable from authentic sample of phloroglucinol and *p*-hydroxy benzoic acid, R_f (phenol) 0.69; R_f (acid) 0.87⁴.

The glycoside m.p. 176–178° on hydrolysis gave an aglycone m.p. 276–278° and a sugar. The aglycone was identified as kaempferol as described earlier and sugar as glucose by R_f value and co-chromatography on Whatman paper No. 1 as well as by TLC. The methylation of the glycoside followed by hydrolysis gave 3-hydroxy-5,7,4'-trimethoxy flavone, m.p. 149–150°⁵, thereby locating the sugar residue at 3-position.

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The glycoside m.p. 217–219° gave a pinkish-red colour with magnesium hydrochloric acid and greenish brown with ferric chloride. U.V. absorption: λ_{max}^{EtOH} 2550 and 3550 Å° and minima at 2400 and 2850 Å°. On hydrolysis it gave an aglycone m.p. 314–315°, which responded to acidic cyanidin test². It showed no depression in melting point on admixture with an authentic sample of quercetin. Its identity as quercetin was further confirmed by co-chromatography and also by U.V. spectra: λ_{max}^{EtOH} 267 m μ and 254 m μ . It gave an acetate m.p. 190–192°⁶, and pentamethyl ether of quercetin m.p. 151–152°⁸. The partial methyl-ether m.p. 193–194°, obtained by the complete methylation of the glycoside followed by hydrolysis, was identified as 3-hydroxy-3',4',5,7-tetramethoxy flavone by usual methods. The glycoside m.p. 217–219° has thus been identified as isoquercitrin.

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